

MICRO-MECHANICAL MODEL AND MATERIAL REMOVAL MECHANISM OF MACHINING CARBON FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer composite material exhibits excellent mechanical properties, such as high specific stiffness and strength, which bring its increasing use in aerospace and aircraft structures. These structures made of composites are mostly produced in near-net-shape, but machining processes such as drilling are usually inevitable for satisfying dimensional tolerances, functional and assembly requirements. Due to heterogeneous, anisotropic, and trans-scale characteristics of composites, the material removal mechanism of composites by machining is quite different from that of metals, thus the well-developed analytical and numerical methods of metal machining cannot be directly applied for the machining of composites.

The present paper studies the particular material removal mechanism of machining composites by a micro-mechanical model, and proposes a prediction model of cutting forces based on a two-parameter elastic foundation beam model. The micro-mechanical model of a representative volume element (RVE) in machining a lamina is established with explicit description of the carbon fiber and the matrix. The fiber in the RVE is subjected to cutting forces, and is supported by the rest of the composite. Thus the deflection of the fiber is constrained by the composite surrounding the fiber, which can be modeled as a beam on an elastic foundation. Analytical expressions are established for evaluating the cutting forces and the debonding between the fiber and the matrix using the micro-mechanical model. Different failure modes of fibers with the constraint effect of the surrounding composite can be recognized from the analytical solutions. The effects of variable depths of cutting, different supporting effects on the material removal are presented in the numerical examples. By revealing the fiber deformation, fiber fracture and debonding between the fiber and the matrix, the material removal mechanism is studied for machining carbon fiber reinforced polymer composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite material exhibits excellent mechanical properties, such high specific stiffness and strength, which result into increasing application in aerospace structures. However, the material removal mechanism of composites by machining is quite different from that of metals due to the heterogeneous and trans-scale characteristics of composites [1]. The direct derivation of the mechanism of metal machining can not reveal the complex interaction effect between the fiber and matrix. The particular material removal mechanism of machining composites is still to be revealed in depth.

Extensive studies of machining composites have been done in literature by theoretical, numerical and experimental approaches, see recent reviews [2-4]. Che et al. [2] summarize four categories to study the machining of CFRP: experimental studies, analytical studies (particularly for cutting forces and cutting heat), numerical simulation (particularly using the Finite Element Method), and mechanistic method. Experimental studies are most widely carried out in orthogonal machining, drilling, trimming, milling, turning, etc. of CFRP. With the development of advanced numerical analysis techniques and software, numerical simulation of machining CFRP is receiving increasing attention, particularly using the finite element method. Analytical expressions can be derived for predicting cutting forces as well as cutting heat using the macroscopic and microscopic properties of

the work piece. Mechanistic modeling methods predict empirically the force responses in terms of process parameters including the chip dimension, tool and work piece geometries, and tool-work piece interaction effect. In comparison with the mechanistic model, the analytical method can reveal the physical essence of material failure and removal.

By machining experiments, Davim and Reis [5] studied the chips for different fiber orientations by orthogonal machining, and presented the relation of the finished surface with the fiber orientation, material and geometry of tool. Wang et al. [6] and Bhatnagar et al. [7] obtained empirical formulas of cutting forces by fitting the experimental data of cutting tests. Arola and Ramulu [8] found that the cutting force increases with a decrease in positive rake angles, and reaches the highest at a negative rake angle for the fiber orientation between 0 and 75 degrees. They also found that the principal cutting force for fiber orientation in $90^\circ \leq \theta \leq 135^\circ$ decreases with a decrease in rake angle, but they did not give a physical explanation on the observed different phenomena. It is also interesting to study the optimum rake angle for different fiber orientations in the entire range $0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 180^\circ$.

Analytical studies of cutting forces also receive much attention. Various theoretical models [9-13] are proposed in literature based on beam theory, representative volume method, homogenization method, and continuum mechanics. Everstine and Rogers [13] presented an analytical expression of the cutting force with 0 degree fiber orientation. Bhatnagar et al. [7] extended the classical metal cutting model to derive the cutting and thrust forces of CFRP by assuming the shear plane consistent with the fiber orientation. Based on an assumption of three distinctive cutting regions, cutting forces are derived by Zhang et al. [11] for the fiber orientation lower than 90 degrees. These macroscopic models do not consider the microscopic characteristics of the composites including the fiber, matrix and interface, so that they are not able to explain the material removal at the microscopic scale. From the microscopic point of view, Pwu and Hocheng [9], and Jahromi and Bahr [10] derive the cutting forces based on the classical beam theory by modeling the fiber in a representative volume element as a cantilever beam. The effects of fiber orientations and the cutting depth on the cutting forces are studied, but the constraint effect of the composite surrounding the fiber to be cut is not considered. Gururaja and Ramulu [12] studied analytically the subsurface stress during orthogonal cutting of unidirectional CFRP using a generalized plane strain anisotropic elasticity formulation.

In the present paper, a prediction model of cutting forces based on a two-parameter elastic foundation beam model is proposed. The micro-mechanical model of a representative volume element (RVE) in machining a lamina is established with explicit description of the carbon fiber and the matrix. The fiber in the RVE is subjected to cutting forces, and is supported by the rest of the composite. Thus the deflection of the fiber is constrained by the composite surrounding the fiber, which can be modeled as a beam on an elastic foundation. The shear and normal forces from the supporting composite are applied on the fiber together with the cutting forces. Analytical expressions are established for evaluating the cutting forces and the debonding between the fiber and the matrix using the micro-mechanical model. The different failure modes of fibers with the constraint effect of the surrounding composite can be recognized from the analytical solutions. The effects of variable depths of cutting, different supporting effects on the material removal are presented in the numerical examples. By revealing the fiber deformation, fiber fracture and debonding between the fiber and the matrix, the particular material removal mechanism is studied for machining fiber reinforced polymer composite.

The organization of the rest of this paper is as follows. After introducing a brief description of the micro-mechanical modeling of cutting fiber reinforced polymer material, Section 2 gives the detailed formulations of the fiber deformation based on the elastic foundation beam model, and the solving procedures to obtain the analytical cutting force and the debonding conditions. Numerical examples are presented and discussed in Section 3 for different cutting depths and fiber orientations. Finally, a section with discussion and conclusions closes the paper.

2 A MICRO-MECHANICAL MODEL OF MACHINING FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITE

2.1 Elastic foundation modeling

Firstly, a two-dimensional micro-mechanical model of a representative volume element (RVE) in machining a lamina is established with explicit description of the fiber and the matrix [1, 14]. The fiber in the RVE is subjected to cutting forces, and is supported by the rest of the composite. As indicated in Fig. 1, the cutting force component f_{Ay} is normal to the fiber, and the component f_{Ax} is along the fiber. The deflection of the fiber is modeled as a beam on an elastic foundation, which reflects the constraint effect of the composite surrounding the fiber. The reaction force p_m from the supporting composite is applied on the fiber together with the cutting forces. At the same time, the interface between the fiber and the matrix may debond due to the tension effect. The possible debonding depth is indicated by h in Fig. 1. The bonding force between the fiber and the matrix is indicated by q_b . The deflection of the fiber caused by applied cutting forces is constrained from both sides, i.e. the forces from the supporting composite and the bonding forces. In Fig. 1, a_c is the nominal cutting depth, δ is the bouncing back of the work piece in the finished surface, and r_e is the radius of the cutting tool edge.

Actions of the supporting composite and the bonding layer on the fiber from the both sides are obtained from Ref. [15]. The reaction force p_m from the supporting composite per unit length is expressed as

$$p_m = k_m w - k_{m1} \frac{d^2 w(x)}{dx^2} \quad (1)$$

where the coordinate x is along the fiber direction, w is the deflection of the fiber in the y direction. The local coordinate $x - y$ of the fiber is indicated in Fig. 1. The symbol k_m is the modulus of the supporting composite, which is called the Winkler foundation modulus reflecting the axial effect from the supporting composite. The symbol k_{m1} is the second parameter of the supporting composite, which can be attributed to the shear effect. The fiber to be cut is modeled as a beam on a two-parameter elastic foundation. The supporting composite can be treated as an Equivalent Homogeneous Material (EHM) [14]. The modulus of the EHM may be calculated from the homogenization method [16] or the RVE (Representative Volume Element) method [17]. If $k_{m1} = 0$, the model reduces to the classical Winkler foundation model with the only one parameter k_m .

Fig. 1 A schematic illustration of orthogonal cutting of fiber reinforced polymer composite

Similarly the bonding force q_b between the fiber and the matrix per unit length is expressed as

$$q_b = k_b w \quad (2)$$

The symbol k_b is the equivalent modulus of the fiber-matrix bonding layer. At the onset point of the debonding between the fiber and matrix, the bonding force is equal to the bonding strength between the fiber and the matrix.

Considering the equilibrium of an infinitesimal element of a length dx of the fiber, we can obtain the governing equation [15]

$$E_f I_f \frac{d^4 w(x)}{dx^4} - k_{m1} \frac{d^2 w(x)}{dx^2} + (k_m + k_b) w = 0 \quad (3)$$

where E_f and I_f are the Young's modulus and the moment of inertia of the fiber, respectively. A generalized model of the beam on a elastic foundation is adopted here through including the second parameter which can be used for considering the shear effect of the supporting composite.

2.2 Solution of fiber deformation

The deflection of the fiber and the stress in the fiber caused by the applying cutting forces are solved analytically in this sub-section with consideration of the constraint effects of the supporting composite and the bonding. The solution of Eq. (3) can be written as in Eq. (4), see Ref. [18], while $k_{m1} < (4kE_f I_f)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, which reflects the relation of the shear effect and the axial effect of the foundation.

$$w(x) = C_1 \cos \beta x \cosh \alpha x + C_2 \cos \beta x \sinh \alpha x + C_3 \sin \beta x \cosh \alpha x + C_4 \sin \beta x \sinh \alpha x \quad (4)$$

where C_1 , C_2 , C_3 , and C_4 are constants of integration, and the symbols α and β are computed as

$$\alpha = \sqrt{\lambda^2 + \delta}, \quad \beta = \sqrt{\lambda^2 - \delta} \quad (5)$$

The symbols λ and δ are expressed as

$$\lambda = \sqrt[4]{\frac{k_m + k_b}{4E_f I_f}}, \quad \delta = \frac{k_{m1}}{4E_f I_f} \quad (6)$$

From the interaction between the fiber and the cutting tool, the fiber in question has varying supporting conditions along its axis, thus the fiber can be divided into three segments as illustrated in Fig. 1. (1) For the first segment of the fiber above the tool-fiber contact point A ($x < a_c - r_e$), and (2) the second segment of the fiber between points A and E ($a_c - r_e \leq x \leq a_c - \delta + h$), the governing equation for the first and the second segments reduces to Eq. (7) since there is not the bonding effect.

$$E_f I_f \frac{d^4 w(x)}{dx^4} - k_{m1} \frac{d^2 w(x)}{dx^2} + k_m w = 0 \quad (7)$$

The solution of Eq. (7) is expressed similarly as in Eq. (4), but using $\alpha = \sqrt{\lambda^2 + \delta}$, $\beta = \sqrt{\lambda^2 - \delta}$,

$\lambda = \sqrt[4]{\frac{k_m}{4E_f I_f}}$, and $\delta = \frac{k_{m1}}{4E_f I_f}$. (3) For the third segment of the fiber below point E ($x > a_p - \delta + h$),

the governing equation is the same as in Eq. (3), and the solution is expressed in Eq. (4). By use of the expressions of hyperbolic functions, Eq. (4) can be rewritten in Eq. (8).

$$w(x) = e^{\alpha x} (B_1 \cos \beta x + B_2 \sin \beta x) + e^{-\alpha x} (B_3 \cos \beta x + B_4 \sin \beta x) \quad (8)$$

where the constants B_1 , B_2 , B_3 , and B_4 can be expressed by C_1 , C_2 , C_3 , and C_4 in Eq. (4). At the bottom of the fiber ($x \rightarrow +\infty$),

$$w|_{x \rightarrow +\infty} = 0 \quad (9)$$

Using this boundary condition, we can obtain $B_1 = B_2 = 0$ in Eq. (8).

2.3 Formulation based on exact displacement function

The element formulation for each segment of the fiber based on the exact displacement function derived in Sub-section 2.2 are adopted in the following analysis. As shown in Fig. 2, $\mathbf{d} = \{w_i, \theta_i, w_j, \theta_j\}^T = \left\{w_i, \frac{dw_i}{dx}, w_j, \frac{dw_j}{dx}\right\}^T$ are the degrees of freedom of the element with two nodes i and j , and $\mathbf{r} = \{Q_i, M_i, Q_j, M_j\}^T$ are nodal loads of the element. The stiffness matrix relating \mathbf{d} to \mathbf{r} will be derived. This stiffness matrix simultaneously accounts for the stiffness of the beam element and the stiffness of the foundation directly.

Fig. 2 Nodal degrees of freedom and the corresponding nodal forces

The displacement of the fiber in Eq. (4) can be rewritten as

$$w(x) = \mathbf{b}^T \mathbf{c} = \begin{Bmatrix} \cos \beta x \cosh \alpha x & \cos \beta x \sinh \alpha x & \sin \beta x \cosh \alpha x & \sin \beta x \sinh \alpha x \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Taking the derivative $\frac{dw}{dx}$ of Eq. (10) gives

$$\frac{dw}{dx} = \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha \sinh \alpha x \cos \beta x - \beta \cosh \alpha x \sin \beta x \\ -\beta \sinh \alpha x \sin \beta x + \alpha \cosh \alpha x \cos \beta x \\ \alpha \sinh \alpha x \sin \beta x + \beta \cosh \alpha x \cos \beta x \\ \beta \sinh \alpha x \cos \beta x + \alpha \cosh \alpha x \sin \beta x \end{Bmatrix}^T \begin{Bmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Three segments of the fiber are defined in Sub-section 2.2. The element formulations for the top, middle and the bottom segments are derived below.

2.3.1 The top segment of the fiber ($x < a_p - r_e$)

By evaluating w and $\frac{dw}{dx}$ at $x_O = 0$, $x_A = a_c - r_e$, where the subscripts O and A indicate the two points O and A of the fiber in Fig. 1, we obtain from Eq. (4)

$$\mathbf{d}_{e1} = \mathbf{A}_{e1} \{C_1 \ C_2 \ C_3 \ C_4\}^T \quad (12)$$

The matrix \mathbf{A}_{e1} can be obtained from Eqs. (10) and (11) by inserting $x_O = 0$ and $x_A = a_c - r_e$. The displacement vector $\mathbf{d}_{e1} = \{w_O, \theta_O, w_A, \theta_A\}^T$. From Eq. (12), the coefficient vector $\{C_1 \ C_2 \ C_3 \ C_4\}^T$ is solved and substituted into Eq. (10), then we will get the displacement solution in the first segment as

$$w(x) = \mathbf{b}^T \mathbf{A}_{e1}^{-1} \mathbf{d}_{e1} = \mathbf{N}_{e1} \mathbf{d}_{e1} \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{N}_{e1} can be considered as a shape function matrix.

From Ref. [15], the shear force Q and the moment M in the beam segment shown in Fig. 2 are computed as

$$Q = V(x) + V_1(x) = E_f I_f \frac{d^3 w}{dx^3} - k_{m1} \frac{dw}{dx} \quad (14)$$

$$M = E_f I_f \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \quad (15)$$

where $V(x)$ is the usual contribution from classical beam theory, and $V_1(x)$ is the contribution from a two-parameter foundation. see Ref. [15]. Using the expression of $w(x)$ in Eq.(13), and taking the first and the second derivative of $w(x)$, we can obtain

$$\mathbf{r}_{e1} = \{Q_o \quad M_o \quad Q_A \quad M_A\}^T = \mathbf{H}_{e1} \{C_1 \quad C_2 \quad C_3 \quad C_4\}^T \quad (16)$$

where the entries of 4 by 4 matrix \mathbf{H}_{e1} are functions of α , β , x_o , and x_A . From Eqs. (12) and (16), the relation of the displacement vector \mathbf{d}_{e1} and the load vector \mathbf{r}_{e1} is established by defining the stiffness matrix $\mathbf{k}_{e1} = \mathbf{H}_{e1} \mathbf{A}_{e1}^{-1}$, which is symmetric.

$$\mathbf{r}_{e1} = \mathbf{k}_{e1} \mathbf{d}_{e1} \quad (17)$$

2.3.2 The central segment of the fiber ($a_c - r_e \leq x < a_c - \delta + h$)

For the central segment of the fiber, the stiffness matrix \mathbf{k}_{e2} relating the load vector $\mathbf{r}_{e2} = \{Q_A, M_A, Q_E, M_E\}^T$ and the displacement vector $\mathbf{d}_{e2} = \{w_A, \theta_A, w_E, \theta_E\}^T$ is similarly derived and obtained as

$$\mathbf{r}_{e2} = \mathbf{k}_{e2} \mathbf{d}_{e2} \quad (18)$$

The displacement solution $w(x)$ in the central segment is expressed in Eq. (19). The matrix \mathbf{A}_{e2} can be obtained from Eqs. (10) and (11) by inserting $x_A = a_c - r_e$ and $x_E = a_c - \delta + h$.

$$w(x) = \mathbf{b}^T \mathbf{A}_{e2}^{-1} \mathbf{d}_{e2} \quad (19)$$

2.3.3 The bottom segment of the fiber ($x \geq a_c - \delta + h$)

The third segment of the fiber starts from the debonding point $x_E = a_p + h - \delta$ between the fiber with the rest. From the expression of displacement in Eqs. (4) and (8), and $B_1 = B_2 = 0$ obtained from the condition $w_3|_{z=+\infty} = 0$, the displacement $w(x)$ can be written in Eq. (20).

$$w(x) = \begin{Bmatrix} e^{-\alpha x} \cos \beta x & e^{-\alpha x} \sin \beta x \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} B_3 \\ B_4 \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{b}_{e3}^T \begin{Bmatrix} B_3 \\ B_4 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

Taking the derivative of $w(x)$ gives

$$\frac{dw}{dx} = \begin{Bmatrix} -\alpha e^{-\alpha x} \cos \beta x - \beta e^{-\alpha x} \sin \beta x \\ -\alpha e^{-\alpha x} \sin \beta x + \beta e^{-\alpha x} \cos \beta x \end{Bmatrix}^T \begin{Bmatrix} B_3 \\ B_4 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

The displacement vector $\mathbf{d}_{e3} = \left\{ w_E, \frac{dw_E}{dx} \right\}^T$ can be calculated from Eqs. (20) and (21) by inserting $x_E = a_p + h - \delta$

$$\mathbf{d}_{e3} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{-\alpha x} \cos \beta x & e^{-\alpha x} \sin \beta x \\ -\alpha e^{-\alpha x} \cos \beta x - \beta e^{-\alpha x} \sin \beta x & -\alpha e^{-\alpha x} \sin \beta x + \beta e^{-\alpha x} \cos \beta x \end{bmatrix}_{x=x_E} \begin{Bmatrix} B_3 \\ B_4 \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{A}_{e3} \begin{Bmatrix} B_3 \\ B_4 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

Combining Eqs. (20) and (22), the displacement $w(x)$ can be written in Eq. (23) in terms of the displacement vector \mathbf{d}_{e3} at the point E.

$$w(x) = \mathbf{b}_{e3}^T \mathbf{A}_{e3}^{-1} \mathbf{d}_{e3} \quad (23)$$

The load vector $\mathbf{r}_{e3} = \{Q_E, M_E\}^T$ at the point E can be solved from Eqs. (14) and (15) by inserting the expression $w(x)$ in Eq. (23).

$$\mathbf{r}_{e3} = \begin{Bmatrix} Q_E \\ M_E \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{H}_{e3} \begin{Bmatrix} B_3 \\ B_4 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

From Eqs. (22) and (24), the stiffness matrix \mathbf{k}_{e3} of the bottom segment of the fiber is established to relate the load vector \mathbf{r}_{e3} and the displacement vector \mathbf{d}_{e3}

$$\mathbf{r}_{e3} = \mathbf{H}_{e3} \mathbf{A}_{e3}^{-1} \mathbf{d}_{e3} = \mathbf{k}_{e3} \mathbf{d}_{e3} \quad (25)$$

2.3.4 The global stiffness matrix

From Eqs. (17), (18), and (25), we can obtain the global stiffness matrix by assembling the element stiffness matrices. It should be emphasized that the element stiffness matrices are obtained from the exact displacement formulations considering the elastic foundation effect, which is different from the standard beam element based on the cubic displacement function. It implies that even there are three beam elements, each for one segment, but the displacement solution is accurate. Assembling (17), (18), and (25) gives

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{K} \mathbf{u} \quad (26)$$

The global load vector $\mathbf{R} = \{Q_O, M_O, Q_A, M_A, Q_E, M_E\}^T$, and the global displacement vector $\mathbf{u} = \left\{ w_O, \frac{dw_O}{dx}, w_A, \frac{dw_A}{dx}, w_E, \frac{dw_E}{dx} \right\}^T$.

The displacement vector \mathbf{u} can be solved from Eq. (27), which can be done analytically.

$$\mathbf{u} = \left\{ w_O, \frac{dw_O}{dx}, w_A, \frac{dw_A}{dx}, w_E, \frac{dw_E}{dx} \right\}^T = \mathbf{K}^{-1} \mathbf{R} \quad (27)$$

When the displacement vector is solved, the deflection along the fiber can be calculated for the three segments OA, AE, the bottom segment starting from E using Eqs. (13), (19), and (23).

2.3.5 Debonding condition

In order to solve the deflection of the fiber, the length h of damage should be calculated a priori. At the point E, i.e. the debonding starting point, the bonding force per unit length is calculated in Eq. (28), which is equal to the bonding strength

$$\sigma_b = k_b w_E \quad (28)$$

where k_b is the bonding stiffness of the fiber-matrix interface, w_E is the deflection of the fiber at the debonding point E. Eq. (28) provides a condition to calculate the critical damage length h .

2.3.6 Stress solution in the fiber

The stress solution in the beam is calculated from

$$\sigma = E_f r \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \quad (29)$$

where r is the radius of the fiber. From the displacement solution $w(x)$ in Eq. (4) for the first and central beam segments and Eq. (8) for the bottom beam segment, we solve the second derivatives of $w(x)$ as in Eqs. (30) and (31).

$$\frac{d^2 w(x)}{dx^2} = \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha^2 \cos \beta x \cosh \alpha x - \beta^2 \cos \beta x \cosh \alpha x - 2\alpha\beta \sin \beta x \sinh \alpha x \\ \alpha^2 \cos \beta x \sinh \alpha x - \beta^2 \cos \beta x \sinh \alpha x - 2\alpha\beta \sin \beta x \cosh \alpha x \\ \alpha^2 \sin \beta x \cosh \alpha x - \beta^2 \sin \beta x \cosh \alpha x + 2\alpha\beta \cos \beta x \sinh \alpha x \\ \alpha^2 \sin \beta x \sinh \alpha x - \beta^2 \sin \beta x \sinh \alpha x + 2\alpha\beta \cos \beta x \cosh \alpha x \end{Bmatrix}^T \begin{Bmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

$$\frac{d^2w}{dx^2} = \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha^2 e^{-\alpha x} \cos \beta x - \beta^2 e^{-\alpha x} \cos \beta x + 2\alpha\beta e^{-\alpha x} \sin \beta x \\ \alpha^2 e^{-\alpha x} \sin \beta x - \beta^2 e^{-\alpha x} \sin \beta x - 2\alpha\beta e^{-\alpha x} \cos \beta x \end{Bmatrix}^T \begin{Bmatrix} B_3 \\ B_4 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (31)$$

The curvature $\frac{d^2w(x)}{dx^2}$ should be evaluated piecewise, namely in Eq. (30) for beam segments OA and AE, and in Eq. (31) for the bottom beam segment starting from E. By using Eqs. (12) and (22), $\frac{d^2w(x)}{dx^2}$ is solved for the three beam segments. Then the solution of $\frac{d^2w(x)}{dx^2}$ is substituted into Eq. (29) to evaluate the stress in the three segments of the fiber.

(7) Iterative algorithm to evaluate the damage length h

Since the damage length h is unknown, the computation of Eqs. (27) and (28) should be conducted iteratively. The external cutting force f_{Ay} will be determined from the fracture conditions of the fiber, which requires the computation of the maximum stress in the beam. The solving procedures are summarized below.

- [1]. Assume an undamaged fiber with $h = 0$, there is no debonding between the fiber and the matrix so that only two beam segments need to be calculated, i.e. segment OA, and the infinite segment starting from A;
- [2]. Gradually increasing the cutting force f_{Ay} until the maximum stress in the fiber reaching the tensile strength;
- [3]. Evaluate the displacement and stress at the point A to check if the debonding happens;
- [4]. From Step [3], if no debonding, we get the force f_{Ay}^{frac} from Step [2], which is the minimum force required to cut the fiber; Complete the iteration, go to Step[8].
- [5]. From Step [3], if debonding happens, we should reduce the applying force f_{Ay} to a value f_{Ay}^{debon} which is going to create the debonding;
- [6]. From Step [5], we know the critical force f_{Ay}^{debon} resulting into debonding. It implies that the three beam segments are needed to compute simultaneously. The damage length h and the applying force should be increased iteratively to find the final force f_{Ay}^{df} (with debonding and fiber fracture)

satisfying $\max \left(E_f r \frac{d^2w(h, f_{Ay})}{dx^2} \right) = \sigma^{tensile}$ with the constraints $k_b w_E(h, f_{Ay}) \leq \sigma_b$;

- [7]. The damage length h and the cutting force f_{Ay} are solved from the following optimization problem by an optimality iterative algorithm.

$$\min_{h, f_{Ay}} \left\{ \left(\max \left(E_f r \frac{d^2w(h, f_{Ay})}{dx^2} \right) - \sigma^{tensile} \right)^2 \right\} \quad (32)$$

subject to: $k_b w_3(h, f_{Ay}) \leq \sigma_b$

The initial value of the cutting force f_{Ay} for the iterative process is f_{Ay}^{debon} obtained in Step

- [6]. Finally, we solve the maximum cutting force f_{Ay}^{df} , and the final damage length h_{final} . The position of maximum stress in the fiber, i.e. the position where fracture happens, is solved at the same time.
- [8]. Stop.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The theoretical models derived in previous sections are applied for studying the material removal mechanism at different fiber supporting conditions and different cutting depths. Material properties of fiber and materials are obtained from Refs. [14, 19].

The first parameter k_m of the supporting composite around a fiber is computed using Biot's formula [20]

$$k_m = 1.23 \left[\frac{E_m^* b^4}{C(1-\nu^2) E_f I} \right]^{0.11} \frac{E_m^*}{C(1-\nu^2)} \quad (33)$$

where C is a coefficient varying from 1 for uniform pressure distribution to 1.13 for uniform deflection. Here $C=1.05$ is simply adopted. In the numerical studies, the second parameter of composite is ignored by assuming $k_{m1}=0$, which implies that a classical Winkler foundation is adopted.

First, the example of cutting the unidirectional CFRP with a fiber orientation 90° is presented using the cutting model in Fig. 1. The nominal cutting depth is $200 \mu\text{m}$. The variation of the deflection in the local x-y coordinate and the maximum stress of the fiber along the fiber are shown in Fig. 3 (a,b). It is observed that the deflection of the fiber reaches the maximum at the cutting point, and the maximum stress in the fiber also appear at the cross-section of the fiber at the point A. The fiber will be cut at the point A since the maximum stress at the point reaches the tensile strength of the fiber.

Fig. 3: Strong constraint effect of the surrounding composite and a nominal cutting depth $200 \mu\text{m}$, (a) The deflection of the fiber, (b) The variation of maximum stress of the fiber along the fiber direction

As a comparison with the deformation of fiber with strong constraint effect, the deformation of the fiber with a low supporting stiffness of the surrounding composite is studied. When the modulus E_m^* of the surrounding composite is reduced to 0.8 MPa , the variation of the deflection in the local x-y coordinate and the maximum stress of the fiber along the fiber are shown in Fig. 4 (a,b). By comparing the deflection of the fiber in Fig. 3 (a) and Fig. 4 (a), it can be concluded that when the supporting effect is strong, the fiber deflects significantly around the cutting position, which reflects the strong constraint of the surrounding composite. However, when the constraint effect is weak as in Fig. 4 (a), the deflection curve of the fiber is very similar to a cantilever beam, where the maximum displacement occurs at the tip point O of the fiber. The stress distribution in Fig. 3 (b) and Fig. 4 (b) for strong and weak supports is quite different. The stress in Fig. 3 (b) is symmetrically distributed with respect to the loading position when a large cutting depth $200 \mu\text{m}$ is adopted. In Fig. 4 (b), the stress reaches the maximum at the load position, and the second largest stress occurs below the machining surface, which may induce some damage. The debonding dose not happen for this case.

Fig. 4: Weak constraint effect of the surrounding composite and a nominal cutting depth $200\ \mu\text{m}$, (a) The deflection of the fiber, (b) The variation of maximum stress of the fiber along the fiber direction

The same modulus $E_m^* = 0.8\ \text{MPa}$ is assumed, but a smaller cutting depth $20\ \mu\text{m}$ is adopted, the variation of the deflection in the local x-y coordinate and the maximum stress of the fiber along the fiber are shown in Fig. 5 (a,b). The stress distribution in Fig. 4 (b) and Fig. 5 (b) for larger and smaller cutting depths is quite different. In Fig. 5 (b), the stress reaches the maximum below the load position, which implies that the fiber fractures below the machined surface. It should be emphasized that the debonding dose not happen.

Fig. 5: Weak constraint effect of the surrounding composite and a nominal cutting depth $20\ \mu\text{m}$, (a) The deflection of the fiber, (b) The variation of maximum stress of the fiber along the fiber direction

When the modulus E_m^* of the surrounding composite is reduced to $0.01\ \text{MPa}$, and the large cutting depth $200\ \mu\text{m}$ is adopted, the variation of the deflection in the local x-y coordinate and the maximum stress of the fiber along the fiber are shown in Fig. 6 (a,b). Debonding happens for this case, thus the iterative procedure should be used for calculating the debonding length and the cutting force. Observed from Fig. 6 (b), the stress reaches the maximum below the load position, which implies that the fiber fractures below the machined surface.

Fig. 6: Weaker constraint effect of the surrounding composite and a nominal cutting depth 200 μm , (a) The deflection of the fiber, (b) The variation of maximum stress of the fiber along the fiber direction

4 CONCLUSIONS

A two-parameter elastic foundation model is proposed to study the machining CFRP at the microscopic scale. By explicit description of the carbon fiber and the matrix, the micro-mechanical model of machining a unidirectional CFRP lamina is established by considering supporting and bonding forces from the supporting composite together with the cutting forces on the fiber. Analytical expressions are established for evaluating the cutting forces and the debonding between the fiber and the matrix using the micro-mechanical model. The different failure modes of fibers with the constraint effect of the surrounding composite are recognized from the analytical solutions. When the supporting effect is strong and a large cutting depth is adopted, the fiber fracture at the load position. When the supporting effect is relatively weak and a small cutting depth is adopted, the fiber may fracture below the machined surface, which implies that the fiber seems to pull out. For a weaker support and a large cutting depth, debonding may happen and fiber may fracture below the load position. The effects of variable depths of cutting, different supporting effects on the material removal are presented in the numerical examples. By revealing the fiber deformation, fiber fracture and debonding between the fiber and the matrix, the particular material removal mechanism is found for machining fiber reinforced polymer composite.

The deformation of work piece material below the clearance face will be solved from the fiber crushing under compression. Therefore, the total cutting forces in the global coordinate X-Y will be evaluated by summation of the cutting force, and the contacts forces and friction forces below the clearance face.

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